

Finite Element Simulation of Three Different Rapid Maxillary Expanders: A Generic Model

Michael Bocklet¹, **Farhad Ahmadi**^{2*}, Timothy Tremont¹, Loring Ross¹, Shuchun Sun², Cherice Hill^{1,2}, Hai Yao^{1,2}, and Ildeu Andrade¹

¹Medical University of South Carolina, Charleston, SC,

²Clemson University, Clemson, SC

Scientific Group/Network: Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery

- Although RMEs are largely successful in younger patient populations, they become increasingly less successful in older adolescents and young adult patients; and they are accompanied with negative side effects

- Recent clinical observation suggests that 3D-printed RMEs produce more favorable outcomes with regard to displacement and stress distribution compared to the other types of RMEs.

Objective: To investigate the stress distribution, areas of stress concentration, and displacement caused by three different RMEs in the craniofacial complex during maxillary expansion using finite element analysis

Stress distribution

Traditional RME

Hybrid RME

3D-printed RME

Aside from the mid-palatal suture, stress was greatest at the pterygomaxillary suture which is consistent with other research that indicates the greatest resistance to expansion being at the pterygoid plates of the sphenoid bone

Displacement distribution

Displacement field reflects the resistance to expansion being greatest in the posterior portion of the maxilla. Data shows an increased displacement value in the sutures that are positioned more anteriorly on the 3D model with the greatest displacements being present at the intranasal, nasomaxillary, and mid-palatal (intramaxillary) sutures

